

ON SUMES OF ALMOST PERIODIC (A.P.) MULTI-VALUED FUNCTIONS

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Abstract: This paper examines the basic properties of the sum of almost periodic multivalued functions whose values are compact sets of the space R^n . It is much more difficult to prove that the sum of two almost-periodic (a.p.) multi-valued functions is a multi-valued a.p. function. The first proof of this theorem for a single-valued function was given by G.Bohr. Subsequently, Bochner gave others a definition for unambiguous a.p. functions on which the almost-periodicity of the sum follows directly. Subsequently, it turned out that Bochner's definition is very useful in many other questions of the theory of a.p. functions. Let us now give a definition for multi-valued a.p. functions, according to Bochner, and prove the equivalence of this definition with Bohr's definition.

Keywords: Almost periodic multivalued functions, spaces R^n , equivalence, arbitrary infinite sequence, real numbers, Sum of multivalued numbers

1 INTRODUCTION

In this work considered basic properties almost periodic functions, values are compact sets space R^n . These properties generalizes famous properties unambiguous functions (see [1], [2]). results applicable to research differential inclusions with almost periodic right in parts.

In what follows, via R denoted by the number axis, through $\alpha = \alpha(A, B)$ is the Hausdorff metric on $comp(R^n)$ and $\|A\| = \alpha(A, B)$. Basic concepts theories multi-valued functions are indicated in [5].

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2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Let $F(t) = R \rightarrow comp(R^n)$ is α -continuous ambiguous function. Here are the main definitions

About definition-1. A bunch of E real numbers are called relatively tight if exists such a number $l > 0$, which is in each interval $(a, a + b) \subset R$ length l contained Although would be one number of many E .

About definition-2. The number τ is called ε -almost-period (ε -a.p.) of the multivalued functions $F(t) = R \rightarrow comp(R^n)$ if

$$\sup(F(t + \tau), F(\tau)) \leq \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

About definition-3. (Bohr). α -continuous ambiguous function $F(t) = R \rightarrow comp(R^n)$ is called ε -almost-period (ε -a.p.), if for each $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists relatively dense set of ε -almost-periods this functions.

Each periodic ambiguous function is also a.p. functions. In the very in fact, if w period F , then all numbers of the form nw ($n = \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots$) also is periods F , and therefore -almost-periods F for any $\varepsilon > 0$. It remains to note that a bunch of nw relatively tight.

Note elementary properties multi-valued a.p. functions that should directly from their definitions.

and if $F(t)$ - multi-valued a.p. function, then $\lambda F(t)$ ($\lambda \in R$) also ambiguous a.p. functions.

If $F(t)$ - multi-valued a.p. functions, then $F(t + c)$ (c - real number) also ambiguous a.p. functions.

About definition-4. α -continuous multivalued function $F(t): R \rightarrow comp(R^n)$ is called a normal function if the family of multivalued functions $\{F(t + h)\}$ ($-\infty < h < \infty$) is compact in the sense of uniform convergence in α the -metric on the entire R , that is, if an infinite sequence of functions

$$F(t + h_1), F(t + h_2), F(t + h_3), \dots$$

a subsequence uniformly converging on the whole R .

1-theorem. In order for α -continuous multi-valued function $F(t): R \rightarrow comp(R^n)$ to be a.p. function, it is necessary and sufficient for it to be a normal function.

Proof. Necessity. Let $F(t): R \rightarrow comp(R^n)$ a multi-valued a.p. function and $h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots$ an arbitrary

infinite sequence of real numbers. It should be shown that from

$$F(t + h_1), F(t + h_2), F(t + h_3), \dots$$

sequence, we can choose a uniformly convergent subsequence. Let's use the diagonal method. Let us denote by

$t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots$ countable, everywhere dense set of real numbers. Since $F(t)$ is bounded (see Theorem 1 [6]), then from the sequence

$$F(t_1 + h_1), F(t_1 + h_2), F(t_1 + h_3), \dots$$

we can choose a convergent subsequence:

$$F(t_1 + h_{11}), F(t_1 + h_{12}), F(t_1 + h_{13}), \dots$$

Likewise for the number sequence

$$F(t_2 + h_{11}), F(t_2 + h_{12}), F(t_2 + h_{13}), \dots$$

we can choose a convergent subsequence:

$$F(t_2 + h_{21}), F(t_2 + h_{22}), F(t_2 + h_{23}), \dots$$

Let's continue this process and then consider the diagonal sequence of functions

$$F(t + h_{11}), F(t + h_{22}), F(t + h_{33}), \dots \quad (2)$$

Let us show that the diagonal sequence (2) converges at all points of a countable, everywhere dense set.

In fact, let be t_k an arbitrary point on a countable set of points. According to our construction, the sequence

$$F(t_k + h_{k1}), F(t_k + h_{k2}), F(t_k + h_{k3}), \dots \quad (3)$$

converges, and for $n > k$ ($t = t_k$) all terms of sequence (2) also converge into sequence (3).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Therefore, sequence (2) converges at any point t_k . Let us now show that sequence (2) converges on the entire R .

Let t_0 be an arbitrary real number and $\varepsilon > 0$. Let us choose a number $l = l\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{5}\right)$ according to Definition 1 and

a number $\delta = \delta\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{5}\right)$ according to Theorem 2 (see [6]).

We cover the interval $[0, l]$ with intervals δ and in each of the intervals of length δ we select a point from a countable everywhere dense set. Let us denote the selected points by $s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_p$. At fixed ε p is also fixed, therefore, from the convergence of sequence (1) at points $s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_p$ it follows that it is possible to specify such a sufficiently large integer $N = N(\varepsilon)$ such that the following inequalities $r, i > N = N(\varepsilon)$ are satisfied p :

$$\alpha\left(F(s_j + h_{rr}), F(s_j + h_{ii})\right) < \frac{\varepsilon}{5}, \quad (j = \overline{1, p}) \quad (4)$$

Let τ almost-period of a multi-valued function $F(t)$ enclosed in $(-t_0, -t_0 + l)$. Then the numbers $s_0 = t_0 + \tau$ lie in $(0, l)$ and therefore, for some j $|s_j - s_0| < \delta$. Hence,

$$\alpha\left(F(s_j + h_{kk}), F(s_0 + h_{kk})\right) < \frac{\varepsilon}{5}, \quad (k = 1, 2, \dots) \quad (5)$$

From inequalities (4) and (5) it follows

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha\left(F(t_0 + h_{rr}), F(t_0 + h_{ii})\right) &\leq \alpha\left(F(s_0 + h_{rr}), F(s_0 + h_{rr})\right) \\ &+ \alpha\left(F(s_0 + h_{rr}), F(s_j + h_{rr})\right) + \\ &+ \alpha\left(F(s_j + h_{rr}), F(s_j + h_{ii})\right) \\ &+ \alpha\left(F(s_j + h_{ii}), F(s_0 + h_{ii})\right) \\ &+ \alpha\left(F(s_0 + h_{ii}), F(t_0 + h_{ii})\right) < \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

And since N does not depend on the number t_0 , but t_0 were ε chosen arbitrarily, then (1) converges uniformly on R . The need has been proven.

Sufficiency. Let $F(t): R \rightarrow \text{comp}(R^n)$ α is a continuous multivalued function on R and the family $\{F(t + h)\}$ ($-\infty < h < \infty$) is compact. It should be shown that $F(t)$ is a multi-valued a.p. function. Let us assume the opposite, that is, suppose that for some $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0$ it is impossible to specify the corresponding length $l(\varepsilon_0)$. This means that there is a sequence of intervals whose $L_1, L_2, \dots$ lengths $r_1, r_2, \dots$ grow indefinitely so that none of the intervals L_n contain ε_0 almost-periods multivalued functions $F(t)$.

Let, h_1 be an arbitrary number and h_2 be chosen so that $h_2 - h_1$ it lies in the interval $L_{v_1} = L_1$. Choose L_{v_2} what $r_{v_2} > |h_2 - h_1|$ and number h_3 so that both numbers $h_3 - h_1$ and $h_3 - h_2$ lie in the interval L_{v_2} . We select the interval L_{v_3} from the condition,

$$r_{v_3} > \max\{|h_2 - h_1|, |h_3 - h_2|, |h_3 - h_1|\},$$

and a number h_4 such that both numbers $h_4 - h_1, h_4 - h_2, h_4 - h_3$ lie in the intervals L_{v_3} . In general, L_{v_n} , we choose so that

$r_n > \max_{1 \leq \mu < \nu \leq n} \{|h_\mu - h_\nu|\}$ and h_{n+1} so that the numbers $(h_{n+1} - h_m) \in L_{v_n}, (m = \overline{1, n})$. Let us now show that from the sequence of functions

$$F(t + h_1), F(t + h_2), F(t + h_3), \dots$$

You cannot choose a uniformly convergent subsequence

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{t \in R} \alpha(F(t + h_{n1}), F(t + h_{n2})) &= \\ &= \sup_{t \in R} \alpha(F(t + h_{n1} - h_{n2}), F(t)) \\ &< \varepsilon_0 \end{aligned}$$

because by construction all numbers $h_{n1} - h_{n2}$ ($n_1 > n_2$) are in an interval $L_{v_{n_1-1}}$ and none of the numbers in this interval is ε_0 an almost-period of a multi-valued function $F(t)$.

The resulting contradiction completes the proof of the theorem. Note that in [3] via [4] this theorem was proved by a different method.

Let us show that for sets on $comp(R^n)$ the following inequality holds:

$$\alpha((A, B), (A', B')) \leq \alpha(A, A') + \alpha(B, B') \quad (6)$$

Indeed, let it $r = \alpha(A, A')$, $\rho = \alpha(B, B')$ be $\varepsilon > 0$ any. Then $A \subset U_{r+\varepsilon}(A')$, $B \subset U_{\rho+\varepsilon}(B')$ where $U_\alpha(M)$ α is a neighborhood of the set M . For any, $x \in A$, $y \in B$ there exist $x' \in A'$, $y' \in B'$ such that $\|x - x'\| \leq r + \varepsilon$, $\|y - y'\| \leq \rho + \varepsilon$.

Then

$$\rho(x + y, A' + B') \leq \|(x + y) - (x' + y')\| \leq \|y - y'\| < r + \rho + 2\varepsilon$$

Hence,

$$A + B \subset U_{r+\rho+2\varepsilon}(A' + B').$$

Similarly, it is proved that

$$A' + B' \subset U_{r+\rho+2\varepsilon}(A + B).$$

That's why

$$\alpha((A, B), (A', B')) \leq r + \rho + 2\varepsilon$$

4 CONCLUSIONS

Since $\varepsilon > 0$ any, then inequalities (6) are proven.

2-theorem. Sum of multi-valued a.p. functions is also a multi-valued a.p. function.

Proof. *multi* $F(t), Q(t): R \rightarrow comp(R^n)$ - valued a.p. functions. According to Theorem 1, the families $\{F(t + h)\}$, $\{Q(t + h)\}$ ($-\infty < h < \infty$) are compact. It is easy to see that the family of functions $\{F(t + h) + Q(t + h)\}$ ($-\infty < h < \infty$) is also compact. In fact, let, for example, be given a sequence of functions $F(t + h_n) + Q(t + h_n)$. First, we choose a subsequence h'_n , for which the sequence of functions $F(t + h'_n)$ converges uniformly, and then from the subsequence h'_n we select a subsequence h''_n for which $Q(t + h''_n)$ it converges uniformly. Because

$$\alpha(F(t + h) + Q(t + h), F(t) + Q(t)) \leq$$

$$\alpha(F(t + h), F(t)) + \alpha(Q(t + h), Q(t)),$$

then the subsequence $F(t + h''_n) + Q(t + h''_n)$ converges uniformly to the function $F(t) + Q(t)$.

Therefore, the family $\{F(t + h) + Q(t + h)\}$ ($-\infty < h < \infty$) is compact and, therefore, by Theorem 1, it is $F(t) + Q(t)$ a multivalued a.p. function. Let us show that for sets from $comp(R^n)$ the following inequality is true:

$$\alpha((A, B), (A', B')) \leq \max\{\alpha(A, A') + \alpha(B, B')\} \quad (7)$$

Indeed, let $r = \alpha(A, A')$, $\rho = \alpha(B, B')$, $\forall \varepsilon > 0$ any and for certainty $\rho \geq r$. Then

$$A \subset U_{r+\varepsilon}(A'), \quad B \subset U_{\rho+\varepsilon}(B'),$$

$$A \cup B \subset U_{r+\varepsilon}(A') \cup U_{\rho+\varepsilon}(B') \subset U_{\rho+\varepsilon}(A' \cup B').$$

In a similar way it is verified that

$$A' \cup B' \subset U_{r+\varepsilon}(A) \cup U_{\rho+\varepsilon}(B) \subset U_{\rho+\varepsilon}(A \cup B).$$

Where follows (7).

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